

LEAD, MERCURY, AND SELENIUM IN BLOOD AND MILK OF WOMEN FROM THREE GOLD-MINING TOWNS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Lead (Pb) and Mercury (Hg) are the two most potent neurotoxic elements widely occurring in the environment. Both are particularly associated with gold-mining. Babies are especially vulnerable to their toxicity and blood levels of the elements too low to have adverse effects in an adult woman could however lead to highly damaging effects in the foetus via placental transfer or in the infant through breastfeeding. Selenium (Se) is known to play major modifying role in the toxicity of the two elements. This work reports the levels of Pb, Hg, and Se in blood and in milk of 106 women from three different locations in Nigeria. These were the active gold-mining community of Yargalma in Zamfara State; the once active gold-mining town of Iperindo in Osun State; and Ile-Ife, also in Osun State, with a history of only pockets of artisanal gold mining. Inductively-Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry was used to determine Pb and Se, while Hg was determined in the same samples by an Atomic Absorption Spectrometry-based Direct Mercury Analyser. The mean Blood Lead Levels and mean Milk Lead Levels obtained reflected the observable/historic levels of gold mining in the three locations, but the Mean Blood Mercury Levels were similar in the three. Selenium levels, probably reflecting dietary intakes, were significantly lower in Yargalma than in Iperindo and Ile-Ife. At the high exposure region of Yargalma, blood Se was found to significantly anti-correlate with both blood Pb and milk Pb, suggesting there could be a role for Se in regulating Pb levels in blood and milk. The picture of high Pb and very low Se levels indicates that the impact of Pb poisoning would be particularly heightened in Yargalma. Significant correlations between levels of Se and Pb in milk were found with parity of the mother.

Keywords: Lead, Mercury, Selenium. ICP-MS, Blood. Human Milk.

INTRODUCTION

Most people who grew up from infancy to adulthood in Nigeria inevitably are carrying a heavy total body burden of lead today. Despite the eventual phasing out of leaded gasoline from the country around 2003 and increasing awareness of the existence of other common sources of lead exposure, a large proportion of the lead cumulatively ingested over the decades by an adult subject remains locked up in the bones, where its resident time is measured, typically in decades (Pounds and Leggett, 1998).

However, this is not altogether true for women during their child-bearing ages. During pregnancy, and more so during lactation, the increased requirement for calcium provokes the release of this essential element from the bones. In what is commonly described as “biological mimicry,” lead, which has similar chemical properties as calcium, is also co-released into the blood of maternal subjects at these critical peculiar periods (Manton *et al.*, 2003). Unfortunately, there is a sharp age-dependence in human susceptibility to the deleterious effects of lead (Agbo 1997, ATSDR 1999). The implication of this is that while the quantity of endogenously released lead might not be sufficient to produce significant adverse health effects in most adults, they could be disastrous to the foetus who is directly exposed through placental exchange; or the baby who might be over-exposed during lactation – depending on milk intake level and pattern (Counter *et al.*, 2004). It has been estimated that as much as 79% of a woman’s skeletal lead could be mobilized and transferred to the fetus through cord blood during pregnancy; and that transfer during lactation is even higher than during pregnancy (Gulson *et al.*, 1997, 1998, 2009). It has been established that blood lead level falls from pregnancy to pregnancy, and is thus strongly dependent on parity of the woman (Mi-Gyung and Won 2005). The greatest risk for lead toxicity therefore lies with first pregnancies. During pregnancy, elevated lead levels have been associated with gestational hypertension, spontaneous abortion, low birth weight, and impaired neurodevelopment (Barclay, 2012).

Apart from lead, mercury is another neurotoxic element to which foetuses and babies are especially susceptible. Mercury is not only anthropogenic but it is also naturally produced. It has several toxic properties and severely affects the environment and humans (Bose-O’Reilly *et al.*, 2010). Selenium, an essential element and an anti-oxidant, on the other hand is known to mitigate the toxic impact of both Pb and Hg. Any realistic assessment of health impact of Pb and Hg therefore ought to involve a study of Se levels (Curvin-Aralar and Furness 1991, Dorea 2004, Ralston *et al.*, 2008, Ojo *et al.* 2013).

The aim of this study is to determine the levels of lead, mercury, and selenium that could be transferred to foetuses and breastfed babies from their mothers, in regions with low and high external lead exposure in Nigeria; and also to investigate the interactions between the three elements at various relative concentrations. Both Pb and Hg are associated with gold mining. Pb in galena is often found in association with gold ore, while Hg is widely used, especially in small scale and artisanal mining, in the beneficiation processes of extracting gold from the ore. The gold mining environment is therefore adopted in this study as a source of a broad spectrum of Pb and Hg levels. Apart from providing an opportunity to better understand and regulate the important gold mining industry in Nigeria, valuable data is also made available to provide insight into the relationship between Pb, Hg, and Se at various relative concentrations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects and Sites Description

One hundred and six (106) lactating mothers were recruited from three different communities as follows:

(i). Twenty-seven subjects (aged 18 – 38 years) from Yargalma. Yargalma is a gold-mining community in Zamfara State, (Northwest Nigeria). It is a confirmed lead polluted environment (Lo *et al.*, 2012, Ojo *et al.*, 2013).

(ii). Thirty-one subjects (aged 18 – 50 years) from Iperindo. Iperindo is a town in Osun State (Southwest Nigeria), and was once a most-active gold mine – intensely mined for over 50 years, now partially abandoned and left for artisanal miners over the past few decades (Alison-Madueke, 2009). The gold ore from this location is also known to be associated with Pb-bearing sulphide ore (galena) (Garba 2000). Considering the persistence of Pb in the environment, Iperindo could be classified as probably lead polluted.

(iii). Forty-eight subjects (aged 14 – 41 years) from Ile-Ife, the city in which our Institution is based. It is also in Osun State, Southwest Nigeria. This is presumed to be a relatively low lead polluted environment, even though artisanal gold mining is widely practiced around the outskirts of the city (Oketayo and Ojo, 2006).

At Yargalma, Zamfara State, subjects were recruited at the village square, and sample collection was carried out at their residences. At Iperindo and Ile-Ife, subjects were recruited from the government Health Centres, offering subsidized services.

Sample Collection, Preservation, and Preparation

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital Complex (OAUTHC). At Yargalma, sample collection was done in collaboration with the Federal Ministry of Health, as part of its response to the outbreak of mass lead poisoning. Venous blood samples were drawn by qualified medical personnel using vacutainer tubes containing ethylene diamine tetra-acetate (EDTA) as anti-coagulant. Breast milk was obtained by manual expression directly by the mothers into provided clean bottles under the supervision of trained female field assistants. Due efforts, including wearing of gloves by the mothers, were taken to ensure the samples were not contaminated.

Blood and milk samples were stored in a deep freezer (at temperature less than -20°C) prior to sample preparation. This comprised of initial thawing and transfer into appropriate vials in the Clean Room at the Department of Physics and Engineering Physics, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife (OAU). Lyophilization followed at the OAUTHC, also at Ile-Ife, using an Edwards Modulyo Freeze-Drier. The samples were further sterilized by gamma irradiation (20 -30 kGy of Co-60) at the National Radiation Centre, Abuja. For a batch of samples, when the Irradiator at Abuja became unavailable, the Cs-137 source at the Centre for Energy Research and Development of OAU, Ile-Ife, with a much less dose, was used. Lyophilized blood and milk samples were sent to the Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia (IJS), for elemental analyses under an existing sub-contract funded by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Vienna.

Elemental Analyses

At the IJS, Ljubljana, Pb and Se (together with Cd, As, Zn and Cu) were determined in blood and milk samples by Inductively-Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry, ICP-MS; while Hg was determined in the same samples by an AAS-based Direct Hg analyser. Details of the procedures have been published in previous reports (Ojo *et al*, 2013a, 2013b). Elemental concentrations determined in freeze-dried samples at Slovenia were converted back into elemental concentrations in fresh samples by using the wet-to-dry weight ratios previously

determined for each individual sample during preparation, and average literature values for densities of breast milk (1.03) and whole blood (1.054).

As Quality Control measures to assure the accuracy of the values obtained for trace elements in blood and milk from subjects in this study, four Reference Materials (Whole human blood PT-WB1, Whole Blood L-1, Spiked Skim Milk Powder (lower levels) BCR 150, and Whole milk Powder NIST 8435) were analyzed together with the freeze-dried blood and milk samples, and the results obtained compared with given reference/certified values.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Elemental Levels in Blood and Milk of Subjects

As shown on Table 1, the values obtained for the trace elements of interest (Pb, Cd, As, Se, Cu, Zn and Hg) in the four reference materials used for quality control, are in good agreement with the reference values provided.

Tables 2a and 2b show the range and mean values for the elements respectively in blood and in milk samples from adult female subjects from the three study areas. These levels are compared with range for the elements reported in literature. Blood Lead Levels (BLL) of mothers correlated with the known intensity of gold mining in the three regions, as indicated in the Subjects and Sites Description above. In Yargalma, BLL ranged from 7.9 – 86.8 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ (geometric mean 55.6 $\mu\text{g/dL}$); in Iperindo, 5.3 – 53.5 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ (geometric mean 14.5 $\mu\text{g/dL}$) and Ile-Ife, 3.7 – 38.0 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ (geometric mean 9.6 $\mu\text{g/dL}$). The corresponding levels in milk were Yargalma, (2 – 140, geometric mean 45 ng/mL); Iperindo, (1.0 – 14.3, geometric mean 3.5 ng/mL); and Ile-Ife, (0.7 – 16.2, geometric mean 2.6 ng/mL). Mercury levels in blood and in milk are generally similar in the 3 regions, but selenium levels in blood and milk from subjects from Yargalma are depressed relative to levels in subjects from Ile-Ife and Iperindo.. Noting the role of Se in mitigating the toxicity of Pb, the picture of high Pb and very low Se levels in subjects from Yargalma indicates that the impact of Pb poisoning would be particularly heightened in that location.

We also compare the mean blood levels of lead, selenium, copper, and zinc in the lactating subjects from Ile-Ife in this study with BLL in non-pregnant, non-lactating subjects also from Ile-Ife, previously reported by Ojo *et al* (2013a) using similar protocols. Levels of both lead and selenium are different, while levels of copper and zinc remain identical (Figure 1). The significant increase of mean BLL in lactating subjects, about 42% higher than the mean BLL in non-lactating women, confirms the endogenous release of lead into blood during pregnancy and lactation. This is quite similar to results reported by Gulson *et al*, (2003) based on studies from Australia. This data can be used to obtain more accurate values for bone resorption in Physiological Based Kinetic Models.

Correlations Between Elements

Correlations between pairs of elements have been used to suggest association or interactions between such elements. In this work, Pearson product moment correlation coefficients were determined for all possible elemental pairs both in milk and in blood.

Correlations between all possible 15 pairs of the three elements of interest in blood and in milk were investigated. Table 3 shows pairs with statistically significant correlation for at least one of the 3 study areas, evaluated separately. The study areas were evaluated separately because the correlations might as well depend on relative concentrations of the elements. Correlations that are repeated in more than one study area further affirm the relationships.

For instance Mother's age mildly correlates ($p < 0.1$) with Blood Pb (confirming accumulation in bones – which affects blood lead level in lactating mothers). On the other hand, Mother's age significantly correlates negatively ($p < 0.01$) with Blood Se. The fact that the correlation patterns often differ for the various groups, indicate that there are many other factors contributing to these observed correlations. Elucidating these factors could be worthwhile and helpful in management of the issue of lead ingestion through breastmilk. For instance the relationship between lead in blood and in milk is known to change with BLL (Counter *et al*, 2004). Though there was no correlation in Blood Pb vs Milk Pb for all the subjects from Yargalma, however, when only subjects with $BLL \geq 40 \mu\text{g/dL}$ were considered, there was indeed a significant correlation at $p < 0.05$. Significant correlations between levels of some elements (Cu, Zn, Se and Pb) in milk were found with parity of the mother). At the high exposure region of Yargalma, blood Se was found to significantly correlate negatively with both blood Pb and Milk Pb.

Correlations between elements as observed in this work could provide a basis for devising measures to reduce the susceptibility of babies to toxic elements ingested through human milk intake in contaminated communities. For instance, these results show that higher levels of Se in blood is associated with lower levels of Pb in both blood and milk (Table 3). Calcium is known to reduce the release of Pb from bones into blood - although its increased uptake is also known to lead to increase absorption of dietary lead. Dietary supplements of Ca has therefore been previously suggested for pregnant and lactating women as a way of achieving low blood Pb, and consequently low milk Pb. (Barclay and Lie, 2012; USNHCC 1994). A study in April 2003 confirmed that ensuring adequate dietary calcium intake or taking a calcium supplement before pregnancy, during pregnancy and during the entire lactation period decreases the blood lead level in lactating women. Supplemental dietary calcium most likely decreases the amount of calcium and lead that comes out of the mother's bones. Therefore, women can significantly reduce their baby's exposure to lead by getting adequate dietary calcium or taking a calcium supplement during pregnancy and lactation. (Hernandez-Avila *et al*, 2003). From the inverse association between blood Se and milk Pb in this study, perhaps a combination of Se with Ca supplement might be more effective in reducing lead levels in blood and milk, than Ca ingested alone.

This proposal is made even more attractive in situations where long-term massive ingestion of Ca is required before significant reduction in blood lead level could be achieved. To mitigate some of the medical complications associated with such prolonged ingestion of Ca, incorporation of other elements that could act synergistically with Ca to antagonize lead has been proposed. For instance, Sood and Prakash (1998) reported that intramuscular administration of iron significantly improved long-term chelation therapy in severe lead poisoning. According to the U.S. National Institute of Health Consensus Conference on Optimal Calcium Intake (AAPCEH 2005, Désirée 2012), the recommended optimal daily intake of calcium for pregnant and lactating women should be 1200 mg/day. However, Vanderjagt *et al* (2001) have reported that intakes in parts of Northern Nigeria was only 200 mg/day of Calcium. Clearly, in such situation, the co-ingestion of some relevant element,

such as Se being proposed in this study, could result in significant clinical benefits for pregnant and lactating women.

According to the Guidelines on Lead Testing in Pregnant and Breast-Feeding Women, co-published by Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Center for Environmental Health, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry, and Healthy Homes and Lead Poisoning Prevention Branch (Désirée 2012), pregnant women with blood lead levels of at least 5 µg/dL (which will apply, practically to all the subjects in our current study) should be evaluated to identify sources of lead exposure; and counseled to avoid further exposure. In such a situation, it was recommended that a daily intake, through diet or supplements, of 2000 mg calcium and 60 – 120 mg iron be administered. Furthermore, it was recommended that women with BLL higher than 40 µg/dL after childbirth, should refrain from breastfeeding their babies, rather expressing and discarding breast milk until blood lead level decreases to values below this threshold.

The US CDC however added that the recommendations are made for the US population and that they are not appropriate in countries where infant mortality from infectious diseases is high. We propose that based on the very well established adverse impact of lead on the long-term quality of life of children, these same reasonable suggestions should be adopted in Nigeria, while every effort is made to improve personal and community hygiene to minimize the infectious disease burden and associated infant mortality. Adopting such a policy, and implementing it will be a helpful first step in stepping up public awareness (and government's responsibility) on the very critical but largely ignored environment-health nexus in Nigeria.

Curtailling breastfeeding under whatever condition might indeed sound rather extreme in view of the well-established benefits of adequate breastfeeding; but continuing to administer massive amount of lead to infants does not appear to be a better deal (Ettinger *et al.*, 2004, Lozoff *et al.*, 2009). In such dicey situations, efforts should be made to give customized counselling to subjects using Physiologically-based Biokinetic Models. Such efforts are ongoing in our laboratory at the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife (Maza and Ojo, 2016). In general, integrating dietary interventions into the national healthcare as a standard practice would be a quite reasonable measure to address the inevitable endogenous lead exposure in pregnant and lactating mothers in a country such as Nigeria.

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Table 1: Quality Control analysis of trace elements in reference materials

Material		Pb content (ng/g)	Cd content (ng/g)	As content (ng/g)	Se content (µg/g)	Cu content (µg/g)	Zn content (µg/g)	Hg content (ng/g)
Trace elements in whole human blood PT-WB1	Intercomparison mean ± SD	159±16	3.3±0.9	11±3, 6.2±0.2, 8.5±0.7	0.318±0.036	2.05±0.25	33.9±4.2	
	Obtained result average ± SD	169±11 (n=6)	2.3±0.4 (n=6)	7.0±0.4 (n=6)	0.237±0.012	1.96±0.07 (n=6)	25.4±0.8 (n=6)	
Seronorm Trace Elements in Whole Blood L-1	Analytical value ± uncertainty	23±6	0.7±0.3	1.8±0.4	0.0798±0.0054	0.564±0.033	5.5±0.3	2.2±0.2
	Obtained result average ± SD	27.9±0.5 (n=6)	0.51±0.08 (n=6)	2.2±0.2 (n=6)	0.060±0.002 (n=6)	0.582±0.008 (n=6)	4.0±0.1 (n=6)	2.2±0.1 (n=3)
BCR 150 Trace elements in Spiked Skim Milk Powder(lower levels)	Reference values ± uncertainty	1000±40	21.8±1.4			2.23±0.08		9.4±1.7
	Obtained result average ± SD	890 ± 17 (n=3)	21.1±1.4 (n=3)			2.27±0.03 (n=3)		8.5±0.2 (n=3)
NIST 8453 Whole Milk Powder	Reference values ± uncertainty	110±50			0.131±0.014	0.46±0.08	28.0±3.1	
	Obtained result	84±2			0.21±0.003	0.413±0.08	21.8±0.2	

Table 2a: Comparison of levels of Elements in blood from the 3 Nigerian towns and World-wide values

Elements in Blood	Yargalma Mean (Range)	Ile-Ife Mean (Range)	Iperindo Mean (Range)	World-wide survey (Iyengar and Wolttlez, (1988)
Pb (µg/dL)	55.6 (7.9 – 86.8)	9.6 (3.7 – 38.0)	14.5 (5.3 – 53.5)	8 – 26.9
Se (µg/mL)	0.08 (0.06 – 0.10)	0.21 (0.13 – 0.41)	0.20 (0.13 – 2.8)	0.06 – 0.23
Hg (ng/mL)	2.0 (0.8 – 4.5)	2.67 (0.99 – 4.56)	1.73 (0.79 – 3.72)	0.6 – 59

Table 2b: Comparison of levels of Elements in milk from the 3 Nigerian sites and World-wide values

Elements in Milk	Yargalma Mean (Range)	Ile-Ife Mean (Range)	Iperindo Mean (Range)	World-wide survey (Vanderjagf 2001)a; Parr 1983)b
Pb (ng/ml)	45.0 (2-140)	2.6 (0.7 – 16.2)	3.5 (1.0 – 14.3)	0.0 – 41.1 (a)
Se (ng/ml)	12.0 (6 – 63)	22.2 (10.3 – 54.4)	33.8 (13.7 – 184.3)	13.1-33.2 (b)
Hg (ng/ml)	3.2 (0.2 – 72.1)	0.5 (0.1 – 7.6)	0.4 (0.2 – 1.7)	0.64 – 257.1

Table 3: Some correlations between the elements Pb, Hg, and Se in blood and milk

	Yargalma (n=24)	Ife (n=23)	Iperindo (n=16)	Ife + Iperindo (n=39)
Blood-Pb vs	r=0.458	r=0.435	r=0.263	r=0.186
Blood-Se	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.1	p>0.1
Blood-Pb vs	r=0.3128	r=0.005	r=0.817	r=0.539
Milk-Pb	p>0.1	p>0.1	p<0.001	p<0.01
Blood-Hg vs	r=0.2845	r=0.545	r=0.565	r=0.489
B-Se	p>0.1	p<0.01	p<0.05	p<0.01
Blood-Hg vs	r= - 0.399*	r=0.308	r=0.235	r=0.129
Milk-Pb	p<0.10	p>0.1	p>0.1	p>0.1
Blood-Se vs	r=0.3449	r=0.327	r=0.261	r=0.134
Milk-Pb	p<0.10	p>0.1	p>0.1	p>0.1
Milk-Pb vs	r=0.1948	r=0.466	r=0.507	r=0.022
Milk-Se	p>0.1	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.1
Milk-Se vs	r=0.3847	r=0.263	r=0.439	r=0.140
Milk-Hg	p<0.10	p>0.1	p<0.10	p>0.1

* inverse correlation

Fig 1: Blood levels of Lead, Selenum (and two other elements) in Lactating (this Study) and Non-lactating, Non pregnant women (Ojo *et al*, 2013a) in Ile-Ife